

Diazoalkanes: Part II¹. Reactions of Diazoalkanes and a few Nucleophiles with Cyclic α -Methoxymethyleneketones

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Reaction of 2-methoxymethylene derivatives of 1-tetralone and 1-hydrindanone with diazoethane, 2-diazopropane and phenyldiazomethane, and a few nucleophiles has been studied. Diazoethane like diazomethane gives pyrazoline derivatives which on decomposition and hydrolysis affords α -propionylketones. 2-Diazopropane and phenyldiazomethane do not react at all. Nucleophiles such as alkoxides, hydrazines, carbanions derived from ketones and Grignard reagents react with these enol ethers giving products in which methoxyl is replaced by the nucleophiles.

In part I of this series¹, methyl ethers of cyclic α -hydroxymethyleneketones (*e.g.*, I & II, R=H) have been shown to react with diazomethane furnishing unstable Δ^1 -pyrazolines which readily eliminate nitrogen and form methylated products (I & II, R=Me) in good yield. The latter on hydrolysis afford α -acetylketones and the reaction thus constitutes a simple method for the preparation of β -diketones from easily accessible β -oxoaldehydes². With a view to study the scope of the reaction further, the two enol ethers have now been treated with a few more diazoalkanes, such as diazoethane, 2-diazopropane, and phenyldiazomethane. The action of some common nucleophiles like hydrazines, alkoxides, and carbanions on these enol ethers has also been investigated.

The reaction with diazoethane³ was found to follow the same course as with diazomethane, both the enol ethers (I & II, R=H) forming the corresponding Δ^1 -pyrazolines (as III) in good yield. The latter decomposed on heating and furnished ethylated products (I & II, R=Et) which on acidic hydrolysis were further converted into 2-propionyl-1-tetralone and 2-propionyl-1-hydrindanone respectively. These diketones are difficult to prepare otherwise. 2-Diazopropane, obtained by oxidation of acetone hydrazone⁴, on the other hand, failed to react with the enol ethers. Crystalline products were however isolated and identified as the pyrazole (IV) and the substituted hydrazone (VI, R=R'=Me, n=1) respectively. These were formed presumably by the reaction of enol ethers with acetone hydrazone which was present in the reaction mixture along with 2-diazopropane, giving initially the substituted hydrazones (VI, R=R'=Me, n=2 and 1 respectively). The derivative from 1-tetralone underwent further modification on distillation furnishing the pyrazole (IV) through an exchange reaction. Truly enough, the enol ethers (I & II, R=H) when kept in contact with acetone hydrazone in ethereal solution, afforded the aforementioned derivatives (as VI), the one from 1-tetralone on

1. D. Nasipuri and K. K. Biswas, *This Journal*, 1967, **44**, 620; also *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1966, 2963.

2. C. R. Hauser, F. W. Swamer, and J. T. Adams, *Organic Reactions*, 1954, vol. VIII, p. 59.

3. D. W. Adamson and J. Kenner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1551; also *Org. Synth.*, coll. vol. III, 1955, p. 244.

4. A. C. Day, P. Raymond, R. M. Southam and M. C. Whiting, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (C), 1966, 467.

distillation giving the pyrazole (IV) and the other from 1-hydrindanone remaining unchanged. Incidentally, anhydrous hydrazine readily reacted with 2-methoxymethylene-1-tetralone giving the pyrazole (IV) directly, while with 2-methoxymethylene-1-hydrindanone it afforded the acyclic hydrazide (II, OMe replaced by NHNH_2), which could not be cyclised to pyrazole by ordinary methods⁵. The pyrazole (IV) was further converted into naphtho (1',2'-3,4) pyrazole (V) by dehydrogenation with palladium-charcoal.

Phenyldiazomethane, prepared by the oxidation of benzaldehyde hydrazone⁶, also failed to react with the enol ethers in the expected manner. Among the products isolated were benzalazine (major part), trans stilbene (from decomposition of phenyldiazomethane), and the substituted hydrazones (VI) $\text{R}=\text{H}$, $\text{R}'=\text{Ph}$, $n=2$ and 1 respectively). The structure of the last-named compounds was established by actual synthesis from the condensation of the enol ethers (I & II, $\text{R}=\text{H}$) with benzaldehyde hydrazone. It is thus seen that 2-diazopropane and phenyldiazomethane are too unreactive towards the enol ethers; as a result the hydrazones which are unavoidably present in the reaction mixture, react instead giving the substituted hydrazones. The strength of the diazoalkane solutions was not however determined.

The ease with which the enol ethers (I & II, $\text{R}=\text{H}$) add up to a nucleophile (see also Tilak *et al.*⁷) prompted us to study a few more addition reactions with some common nucleophiles. Reaction with methanolic sodium methoxide was expected to lead to an equilibrated mixture of cis and trans-isomers in which the trans compound (I, $\text{R}=\text{H}$) with $=\text{CO}$ and OMe on opposite sides should predominate. The equilibrated product was however a gum and no useful information could be obtained regarding its composition. Reaction of the enol ether (I, $\text{R}=\text{H}$) with potassium *t*-butoxide, on the other hand, furnished a crystalline solid in high yield which was identified by N. M. R spectroscopy (*vide experimental*) as the corresponding *t*-butyl ether (VII, $\text{Y}=\text{OBu}^t$). Apparently the enol ether had undergone an 1,4-addition with the nucleophile and the OMe was eliminated in a subsequent step as shown:

5. R. C. Elderfield, *Heterocyclic Compounds*, Vol. 5, 1957, p. 48.

6. W. M. Jones and Wum-tentai, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **27**, 1324.

7. B. D. Tilak, H. S. Desai and S. S. Gupte, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1966, 1953.

8. D. Lednicer, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, **29**, 2480.

9. W. D. Garden and F. D. Gunstone, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 2650.

Carbanions derived from ketones likewise reacted with the enol ethers forming α,β -unsaturated 1,5-diketones. For example, 1-tetralone condensed with the enol ethers (I, R=H; and VII, Y=OBu^t) in presence of base giving the diketone (VIII) in good yield. The structure of the diketone followed from its N. M. R. spectrum (*vide* experimental). In as much as the above enol ethers are vinylogues of esters, this reaction may be considered as Claisen condensation between an ester and a ketone.

The enol ether (I, R=H) was next treated with an excess of phenylmagnesium bromide*. A highly crystalline compound was isolated from the reaction mixture which was proved to be 2-benzhydryl-1-tetralone (IX), mainly from its N. M. R. spectrum. This was presumably formed by two successive 1,4-additions of the phenyl anion, the first one leading to 2-benzylidene-1-tetralone (X) according to mechanism previously discussed, and the second one leading to the final product. This compound (IX) was also found to be formed in good yield when the benzylidenetetralone (X) was treated with phenylmagnesium bromide. Inverse addition of an equimolecular quantity of phenylmagnesium bromide to the enol ether (I, R=H) also gave exclusively the benzhydryl derivative but not the expected benzylidene-tetralone (X). Apparently, the second step of the reaction, namely, the 1,4-addition to benzylidene-tetralone is a faster reaction than the first. Alternatively, the second step of the process may be visualised as a nucleophilic substitution reaction where methoxyl in the resulting Grignard complex is directly replaced by phenyl, the substitution being facilitated by the participation of the neigh-

*After communication of this paper, our attention was drawn to a publication of Lednicer⁸ describing similar results.

neighbouring magnesium as shown (XI). This mechanism precludes the idea that benzylidene-tetralone is necessarily an intermediate.

Lastly, the enol ethers (I, R=H and Me) were submitted to Reformatsky reaction with zinc and ethyl bromoacetate. The product was mostly tar and no crystalline material could be isolated from it. The monocyclic enol ether (XII), on the other hand, reacted smoothly with the Reformatsky reagent and afforded an oil, which on acidification furnishes a keto-ester which mostly exists in the enol form possibly having the structure and configuration (XIII), as evidenced from its spectroscopic behaviour and its failure to cyclise to α -pyrone derivative.

EXPERIMENTAL

M. p.s. and b. p.s. are uncorrected. The N. M. R. spectra were taken in deuteriochloroform solution in a 60 Mc. machine. The UV spectra were done in ethanol solution unless otherwise stated. Light petroleum refers to a fraction, b. p. 40-60°.

Reaction of 2-Methoxymethylene-1-tetralone (I, R=H) with Diazoethane.— A solution of 2-methoxymethylene-1-tetralone (3.76 g., 0.02 mole) in ether (10 ml.) was kept in with an ethereal solution of diazoethane (0.06 mole), prepared from N-nitroso- β -ethylaminoisobutyl methyl ketone (16.06 g.) and ether (250 ml.). The solution was left at room temperature for 36 hr, filtered and slowly evaporated under reduced pressure without any application of heat. The pale yellow viscous liquid (5.01 g.) thus obtained was dried under vacuum and analysed for nitrogen (Found: N, 10.9, C₁₄H₁₆O₂N₂ requires N, 11.5%). Based on nitrogen content, the crude product contained approximately 95% of the pyrazoline derivative (III). The dry product was gently heated with a naked flame when evolution of nitrogen started. The reaction then grew quite vigorous and the flame was removed. The dark liquid after nitrogen elimination was slowly distilled in vacuum to furnish 2- α -methoxypropylidene-1-tetralone (2.82 g.). Redistillation afforded a colourless viscous oil, b. p. 140-45°/0.3 mm. (Found: C, 77.5; H, 7.9, C₁₄H₁₆O₂ requires C, 77.8; H, 7.4%), which turned pale yellow on keeping and possessed a characteristic odour.

2-Propionyl-1-tetralone—The above methyl ether (2.2 g.) was dissolved in methanol (12 ml.) and water (1.2 ml.), cooled in ice, and concentrated hydrochloric acid (0.5 ml.) was added. The mixture was kept at 0° for 24 hr. and then diluted with water. The organic matter was taken up in ether and the ethereal solution was extracted with 5% aqueous potassium hydroxide (2 \times 15 ml.). The yellow aqueous solution was carefully acidified when crystalline solid separated. This was filtered and crystallised from methanol in shining colourless plates (1.2 g.), m. p. 64° (Found: C, 77.5; H, 7.4. C₁₃H₁₄O₂ requires C, 77.2; H, 6.9%). The diketone thus obtained afforded a green copper derivative (from ethanol), m. p. 179° (decomp.).

Reaction of 2-Methoxymethylene-1-hydrindanone (II, R=H) with Diazoethane.— A solution of 2-methoxymethylene-1-hydrindanone (3.48 g.) in dry tetrahydrofuran (12 ml.) was similarly kept in with diazoethane, prepared from N-nitroso- β -ethylaminoisobutyl methyl ketone (16.06 g.) at room temperature for 36 hr. The brown viscous liquid obtained after evaporation of ether was analysed for nitrogen and found to contain 87%

of the pyrazoline. This was slowly decomposed by heat and distilled. 2- α -*Methoxypropylidene-1-hydrindanone* (2.51 g.) was obtained as a colourless liquid, b.p. 150°/0.6 mm. (Found: C, 76.5; H, 7.5; $C_{13}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 77.2; H, 6.9%), which turned brown on keeping.

2-Propionyl-1-hydrindanone.—The foregoing methyl ether (1.9 g.) was hydrolysed by methanolic hydrochloric acid as described before and the acidic diketone extracted with alkali, *2-Propionyl-1-hydrindanone* (1.05 g.) was obtained as shining plates which was further crystallised from methanol and had m.p. 52° (Found: C, 76.5; H, 7.0; $C_{12}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 76.6; 6.4%). The diketone afforded an olive green copper derivative, m.p. 230° (decomp.) (from ethanol).

Attempted Reaction of 2-Methoxymethylene-1-tetralone with 2-Diazopropane—An ethereal solution of 2-diazopropane was prepared by oxidation of acetone hydrazone (20.0 g.) in dry ether (450 ml.) and 3M ethanolic potassium hydroxide (6 ml.) with yellow mercuric oxide (75.0 g.) The brown red solution of the diazopropane was decanted out and to it added a solution of 2-methoxymethylene-1-tetralone (3.76 g.) and the whole kept at 0° for 24 hr. The ether was removed under reduced pressure and the residue distilled to afford a red highly viscous glassy mass (3.0 g.), b.p. 180°/0.3 mm. On scratching it solidified and was further crystallised from benzene to furnish colourless needles, m.p. 125°. It analysed for the *pyrazole* derivative (IV) (Found: C, 77.85; H, 5.9; N, 16.2. $C_{11}H_{10}N_2$ requires C, 77.65; H, 5.9; N, 16.5%). The N. M. R. spectrum showed four aromatic protons, one at 1.95 T and three at 2.50 T , one =CH proton of pyrazole ring at 2.38 T , and four benzylic and allylic protons at 7.0 T . The compound was synthesised as described below.

3,4-Dihydronaphtho (1',2'-3,4) pyrazole (a) To a solution of 2-methoxymethylene-1-tetralone (I, R=H) (1.88 g.) in dry ether (8 ml.) anhydrous hydrazine (0.64 g.) was added. A deep red oil separated which readily solidified and adhered to the walls of the flask. It was left over night at room temperature. The solid obtained after evaporation of ether was crystallised from benzene to furnish colourless needles, (1.45 g.), m.p. 125° (Found: C, 77.6, H, 6.0%). It showed no depression in m.p. when admixed with a sample described above.

(b) Acetone hydrazone (0.72 g.) was added to a solution of 2-methoxymethylene-1-tetralone (1.88 g.) with shaking. A deep yellow colour developed which slowly changed to orange red. It was left at room temperature for 24 hr., ether was evaporated off, and the residue distilled in vacuum. A glassy mass (1.5 g.), b.p. 180°/0.3 mm. was obtained which solidified on scratching. On twice crystallisation from benzene the pyrazole (IV) was obtained in pure state, m.p. and mixed m.p. 125°.

Naphtho (1',2',-3,4) pyrazole (V).—The above pyrazole (IV) (0.7 g.) was refluxed with 10% palladium-charcoal (0.3 g.) in *p*-cymene (25 ml.) at 180-185° for 2.5 hr. The solution was filtered hot, the filtrate concentrated and allowed to stand at room temperature. Flocculent precipitate appeared which was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to afford the *naphthopyrazole* (V) in shining colourless needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 163° (Found: C, 78.5; H, 5.0; N, 16.9; $C_{11}H_8N_2$ requires C, 78.6; H, 4.8; N, 16.7%). In the N.M.R spectrum, all the protons appeared in the aromatic region (below 2.75 T).

Attempted Reaction of 2-Methoxymethylene-1-hydrindanone (II, R=H) with 2-Diazopropane—A solution of 2-methoxymethylene-1-hydrindanone (3.48 g.) in tetrahydrofuran (12 ml.) was likewise kept in with an ethereal solution of 2-diazopropane, prepared from acetone hydrazone (20.0 g.), yellow mercuric oxide (75.0 g.) and ether (450 ml), at 0° for 24 hr. The material after evaporation of ether was heated upto 140° to remove any unreacted acetone hydrazone and acetone azine. The residue in the flask solidified and was sublimed at 145-150°/0.2 mm. to afford yellow crystalline mass (3.6 g.), m.p. 128°. Once crystallisation from benzene furnished shining yellow plates, m.p. 129° (Found: C, 72.6; H, 6.6; N, 13.3. C₁₃H₁₄ON₂ requires C, 72.9; H, 6.5; N, 13.1%). The N.M.R. spectrum was in agreement with the structure (VI, R=R'=Me, n=1) it showed a multiplet at 1.92 T (1H, C₇-H of the hydrindanone moiety), multiplet at 2.25 T (4H; three aromatic protons and one side chain proton, =CH-N), a singlet at 6.25 T (2H, benzylic protons), a singlet at 7.87 T (6 H, isopropylidene protons). The substituted *hydrazone* (VI, R=R'=Me, n=1) was prepared as follows.

Synthesis of the Hydrazone (VI, R=R'=Me, n=1)—Acetone hydrazone (0.72 g.) was added to a solution of 2-methoxymethylene-1-hydrindanone (1.74 g.) in tetrahydrofuran (8 ml.) with shaking. After 24 hr. at room temperature, solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue readily solidified into a red mass (2.0 g.) which was sublimed at 145-150°/0.2 mm. to afford a yellow crystalline solid, m.p. 128°. One crystallisation from benzene gave shining yellow plates, m.p. 129° which showed no depression in m.p. when admixed with a sample described above. It had λ_{max} . 224 m μ (log ϵ 3.84), and 258 m μ (log ϵ 3.97), and 301 m μ (log ϵ 3.52); ν_{max} . 3675, 1701, 1655 cm⁻¹ etc.

Reaction of 2-Methoxymethylene-1-hydrindanone (II, R=H) with Hydrazine. Formation of 2-Hydrazidomethylene-1-hydrindanone—To a solution of 2-methoxymethylene-1-hydrindanone (0.87 g.) in tetrahydrofuran (8 ml.), anhydrous hydrazine (0.16 g.) was added with shaking. Heat was evolved and a highly crystalline mass began to separate from the reaction mixture. The solid was collected and crystallised from methanol-benzene in shining orange-yellow plates (0.71 g.), m.p. 148° (Found: C, 68.7; H, 6.0; N, 15.65. C₁₀H₁₀ON₂ requires C, 69.0; H, 5.75; N, 16.1%). It remained unchanged on distillation.

Attempted Reaction of 2-Methoxymethylene-1-tetralone with Phenyl diazomethane.—A solution of 2-methoxymethylene-1-tetralone (I, R=H) (3.76 g.) in dry ether (10 ml.) was kept in contact with phenyl diazomethane, prepared from benzaldehyde hydrazone (25 g.), red mercuric oxide (50 g.) and light petroleum (250 ml.) at 0° for 7 days. A deep yellow crystalline solid (4.0 g.) was deposited on the walls of the flask which was collected by decantation and crystallised from methanol in thin yellow plates, m.p. 126.5°. It analysed for the substituted benzaldehyde *hydrazone* (VI, n=2, R=H; R'=Ph) (Found: C, 78.2; H, 5.9; N, 10.7. C₁₈H₁₆ON₂ requires C, 78.3; H, 5.8; N, 10.14%). The same compound was also obtained when a solution of 2-methoxymethylene-1-tetralone was treated with benzaldehyde hydrazone in ethereal solution.

The mother liquor from the previous reaction was distilled from a water-bath and the residue cooled in ice when crystalline benzalazine, m.p. 93° separated (yield, 13.0 g.). After removal of the azine, a syrupy liquid was left behind which was distilled and the following fractions collected: (i) an oil, b.p. 160-170°/600 mm. (2.0 g.) which proved to be mostly benzaldehyde; (ii) a solid (0.5 g.), b.p. 140-150°/5 mm., which on crystallisation from methanol afforded white flakes, m.p. 124°. This was proved to be *trans* stilbene from

its m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample; (iii) a third fraction (4.0 g.), b.p. 180-190°/0.2 mm. (brown solid) which was found to be benzalazine on crystallisation; (iv) a red viscous mass (3.4 g.) was left behind which could not be distilled.

Attempted Reaction of 2-Methoxymethylene-1-hydrindanone with Phenyl diazomethane—The reaction was carried out in a similar fashion as described above. From the methyl ether (3.48 g.), and phenyl diazomethane prepared from benzaldehyde hydrazone (25 g.) and red mercuric oxide (50 g.), the following compounds were isolated: (i) the substituted *hydrazone* (VI, R=H, R'=Ph) (4.5 g.), m.p. 223° (from methanol) (Found: C, 77.9; H, 5.5; N, 10.3 C₁₇H₁₄ON₂ requires C 78.3; H, 5.3; N, 10.7%). (This was found to be identical with a sample prepared by condensation of the enol ether (II, R=H) with benzaldehyde hydrazone); (ii) benzalazine and (iii) *trans stilbene* as in the previous experiment.

2-t-Butoxymethylene-1-tetralone (VII, Y=OBu^t).—To a solution of potassium *t*-butoxide in *t*-butanol, prepared from potassium (0.22 g.) and *t*-butanol (5 ml.), a solution of 2-methoxymethylene-1-tetralone (I, R=H) (0.94 g.) in *t*-butanol (2 ml.) was added. A deep violet colour developed and the mixture was stirred for two hr. and then left overnight. The mixture was then diluted with water, extracted repeatedly with ether, the ether extract washed with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Solvent was removed and the residue distilled in vacuum to afford a yellow syrupy liquid (0.6 g.), b.p. 145-150°/0.6 mm. which readily solidified to a crystalline mass. The *t*-butyl ether thus obtained was crystallised from light petroleum in colourless plates, m.p. 82° (Found: C, 77.98; H, 7.70; C₁₅H₁₈O₂ requires C, 78.25; H, 7.8%). The N. M. R. spectrum consisted of the following peaks: a multiplet at 1.87 *T* (1H, C₈-H of the tetralone moiety), a singlet at 2.04 *T* (1H, =CH-O in the side chain), multiplet at 2.67 *T* (3H, aromatic), a broad peak at 7.16 *T* (4H, two methylene protons of the tetralone moiety), and a sharp singlet at 8.58 *T* (9H, *t*-butyl group).

Condensation of 2-Methoxymethylene-1-tetralone with Tetralone.—Formation of the Diketone (VIII).—To a solution of potassium *t*-butoxide prepared from potassium (0.44 g.) and *t*-butanol (10 ml.), a mixture of 2-methoxymethylene-1-tetralone (1.88 g.) (or equivalent amount of the corresponding *t*-butyl ether) and 1-tetralone (1.46 g.) in *t*-butanol (5 ml.) was added and the mixture stirred for 2 hr. A deep violet colour developed. After 20 hr., the mixture was diluted with water, the organic matter extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed with water till the washings were neutral, and then dried over Na₂SO₄. Removal of ether afforded a yellow crystalline solid (2.8 g.), which on twice crystallisation from ethanol furnished the *diketone* (VIII) as golden yellow needles, m.p. 139° (Found: C 83.3; H, 6.2. C₂₁H₁₈O₂ requires C, 83.4; H, 6.0%); λ_{max}. 262 μ. (log ε, 4.39). The N. M. R. spectrum consisted of the following peaks: multiplets at 1.89 *T* (2H; C₈-H's of the tetralone moieties), multiplets at 2.58 *T* (6 H, aromatic protons), a doublet at 2.95 *T* (1H, side chain =CH-), a multiplet at 6.34 *T* (1H, -COCH-) a broad multiplet centred at 7.00 *T* (6H, two benzylic and one allylic methylenes), and another multiplet at 7.70 *T* (2H, the remaining methylene of one of the tetralone moiety).

Action of Phenylmagnesium Bromide on 2-Methoxymethylene-1-tetralone. (a) Formation of 2-Benzhydryl-1-tetralone (IX).—To the Grignard reagent prepared from bromobenzene (4.71 g., 0.03 mole), magnesium (0.8 g.), and dry ether (25 ml.), a solution of 2-methoxymethylene-1-tetralone (3.76 g., 0.02 mole) in ether (10 ml.) was added dropwise

with stirring. A solid complex separated out which was stirred for 1 hr. and then refluxed for an additional hr. The mixture was then decomposed with ice-cold 3N sulphuric acid. The ethereal layer was separated, washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and then with water, and dried over Na_2SO_4 . The residue after evaporation of ether, was distilled, and a middle fraction (2.5 g.), b.p. 230-235/0.4 mm. was collected as a red glassy mass. On crystallisation from a large volume of methanol, it afforded 2-benzhydryl-1-tetralone (IX) as shining colourless plates (1.70 g.), m.p. 150°, lit⁹ m.p. 147-148° (Found: C, 88.3; H, 6.2. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$ requires C, 88.5; H, 6.4%). The N. M. R. spectrum showed the following peaks: A multiplet at 2.00 T (1H, $\text{C}_8\text{-H}$ of the tetralone moiety), irregular multiplets centred at 2.73 T (13 H, aromatic protons), a doublet at 5.25 T ($J=8.5$ cps) (1H, benzhydryl proton), a multiplet containing six well-defined peaks at 6.50 T (1 H, $\text{C}_2\text{-H}$ of the tetralone moiety), a triplet at 7.02 T (2H, benzylic methylene), and finally a multiplet consisting of six ill-defined peaks centred at 7.91 T (2H, the homobenzylic methylene of tetralone moiety).

2-Benzhydryl-1-tetralone afforded red dinitrophenylhydrazone which crystallised from benzene-ethanol in bright red plates, m.p. 226° (Found: C, 70.5; H, 5.0; N, 11.8. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$ requires C, 70.7; H, 4.9; N, 11.4%).

(b) *Inverse Addition of the Grignard Reagent.*— A solution of phenylmagnesium bromide from bromobenzene (3.14 g., 0.02 mole), magnesium (0.5 g.) and ether (16 ml.) was added dropwise with stirring to a solution of 2-methoxymethylene-1-tetralone (3.76 g., 0.02 mole) in ether (15 ml.) The mixture was refluxed for two hr. and then worked up in the usual way. The product on distillation afforded a fraction (1.5 g.), b.p. 230-235°/0.4 mm. which was crystallised from methanol in colourless plates, m.p. 150°, and was identical with 2-benzhydryl-1-tetralone.

2-Benzylidene-1-tetralone (X) This was prepared in the usual method by condensing benzaldehyde with 1-tetralone in presence of 15% sodium hydroxide solution. It had m.p. 109° (from ethanol).

Reaction of Phenylmagnesium Bromide with 2-Benzylidene-1-tetralone.— To a solution of 2-benzylidene-1-tetralone (2.34 g.) in dry benzene (25 ml.), phenylmagnesium bromide, prepared from bromobenzene (1.57 g.), magnesium (0.27 g.), and ether (12 ml.) was added dropwise with stirring. The mixture was refluxed for two hr. and then decomposed with ice and acid. The product was worked up in the usual way and afforded 2-benzhydryl-1-tetralone (2.1 g.), m.p. 150° on distillation and subsequent crystallisation.

Reformatsky Reaction of 2- α -Methoxyethylidenecyclohexan-1-one (XII).— 2-Methoxyethylidenecyclohexanone (XII) (9.24 g.) and freshly distilled ethyl bromoacetate (10.32 g.) were dissolved in 1:1 benzene-tolunene (50 ml.) A portion of this solution (10 ml.) was added to activated zinc powder (3.96 g.) heated to about 95° with stirring. The reaction soon started and the rest of the solution was added during 1 hr. keeping the temperature at 95°. Heating and stirring was continued until almost all the zinc was dissolved. The mixture was then cooled in ice and the complex hydrolysed by addition of 25% sulphuric acid (60 ml.) The benzene layer was separated washed thoroughly with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution to remove 2-acetylcyclohexanone if any, and the solvent evaporated. The residue was distilled and a fraction (3.5 g.), b.p. 105°/10mm.

having a sweet odour was collected. It analysed for ethyl 2-acetylcyclohexylidene acetate (XIII) (Found: C, 67.9; H, 8.3. $C_{12}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 68.6; H, 8.6%); λ_{max} , 290m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.91); ν_{max} 3675, 2925, 1700 cm^{-1} , etc.

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